

Elucidating self-organized feedback-based generic phenotypic plasticity mechanisms in living matter

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EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Phenotypic-plasticity of living organisms, defined as their ability to robustly adapt to short-term environmental change, is one of the their most essential survival-oriented structural characteristics (see for instance DeWitt and Scheiner (2004)). This fundamental property of living matter comes as a result of self-organized feedback-based regulation of the so-called genotype-to-phenotype map, *i.e.* the informational operator that causally relates the full genome of a given individual organism to its corresponding phenotypic space (see for instance Espinosa-Soto et al. (2011); Kaneko (2012) and the references therein). The traditional approach to tackle the understanding of the interaction between the environment and the complex dynamical behaviour of the genotype-to-phenotype map is based on the so-called reaction norm phenomenological model, as thoroughly exposed in the seminal book by West-Eberhard (2003)). Such a phenomenological approach quantifies the contribution of environmental variation to observed phenotypic variation, shaping for this a phenomenological curve just named *norm of reaction* (also understood as the range of phenotypes produced by a particular genotype in different environmental conditions).

However, such a traditional approach is quite constrained when considering the uncovering of the systems based robust causal generic gene regulatory principles underlying phenotypic plasticity. These feedback-based regulatory principles define a self-organized cell-dynamics ballet that results from the highly complex interplay between:

- developmental processes,
- physicochemical fields,
- environmental signals,
- cell lineage,
- cell-to-cell communications,
- as well as intrinsic and extrinsic stochastic noise.

In recent years the limitations of the non predictive phenomenological reaction norm model have been clearly exposed. As discussed in Pfennig and Ehrenreich (2014), these inherent limitations of the traditional approach ask for the development of a systems based mechanistic predictive perspective. Fortunately, the emergency in recent times of the systems biology scientific field has opened the door to go beyond the phenomenological reaction norm model. Our aim here is to contribute to the development of such a systems biology based approach, following for this a mathematical and computer based systems biology methodological perspective. Mathematical systems theory is then at the heart of our proposal. Thus, we focus our attention on the elucidation of the system based consequences of short-term environmental change onto the dynamical shaping of the stochastic epigenetic landscapes that underlie developmental core gene regulatory processes

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Fig. 1. Gene Regulatory Network underlying cell-type subdifferentiation in *A. thaliana* root epidermis. In this figure the nodes in yellow correspond to the control elements of the phosphate response. The nodes in white correspond to the genes involved in the determination of the identity of trichoblasts and atrichoblasts. The nodes in pink correspond to the elements of hormonal regulation. The nodes with two degraded colors correspond to nodes that integrate two identified different pathways of regulation. Green lines correspond to positive interactions while red lines correspond to negative interactions. The continuous lines correspond to direct interactions obtained through bibliographic research while the dotted lines correspond to bioinformatic inferences or assumptions of the model.

(see Huang (2011); Villarreal et al (2012), and the references therein). We choose a morphogenetic phenomenon in order to illustrate this stochastic nonlinear process. We proceed then to the mathematical and computer based study of the phenotypic plasticity dynamics that characterize *Arabidopsis thaliana* root-hair cell-fate. We must point out that we choose this structure model due to its clear morphogenetic spatiotemporal manifestation at the tissue-level, which is relatively easy to track in experimental terms. Thus, inspired by the pioneering work by Turing and Meinhardt¹ (see Turing (1952); Gierer and Meinhardt (1972); Meinhardt (2012)), and based on some previous theoretical and experimental results obtained by our research team (see Benitez et al (2008); Benitez and Alvarez-Buylla (2010)), our point of departure is the development of a robust qualitative discrete spatial mathematical model of the multi-stable core gene regulatory network that modulates root-hair cell fate (see Figure 1). Then, we introduce a systemic methodological procedure that uncovers the systems based environmental circumstances that dynamically shape the stochastic epigenetic-landscape that underlies the regulatory processes that give rise to the root-hair pattern-formation. Finally, we explore the short-term response that the involved multi-stable core gene regulatory network gives to some chosen specific exogenous stimuli that code short-term environmental change. For

¹ Who figured out the key roles played in morphogenetic processes by biochemical activation/inhibition nonlinear interactions, like the ones that drive biochemical reaction-diffusion processes.

our case the explored environmental signals quantify the concentration of the phosphate available in the soil material (see Figure 2). Our formal systemic methodological approach successfully predicts the self-organized *Arabidopsis thaliana* root-hair spatial patterning formation, and provide some insights into the sufficient structural complex generic mechanisms that causally explain it.

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Fig. 2. Effects of phosphate deficiency on the root hair density. Root hair density was determined as the number of hairs in a 1 cm root segment on 22 7-day-old seedlings from each line. (A) Quantitative analyses of root hair density. Data represent mean \pm SD and the asterisks indicate significant differences to +P based on two-way ANOVA was followed by the Bonferroni test. (B) Representative images of root hair formation in seedlings grown in +P or -P media.

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